

CTRL+ALT+EVOLVE: THE DIGITAL REBIRTH OF RECORDS TRANSFER

A CASE-STUDY IN REIMAGINING DIGITAL RECORDS TRANSFER AT THE UK NATIONAL ARCHIVES

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Abstract – This case study explores the theme of **Haerenga (Journey)**. It charts the transformation of the born-digital records journey from depositors into the custody of the UK National Archive for permanent preservation; and explores the ongoing evolution of this journey as we work to make it faster and more intuitive. Along the way, we discuss the journey of the institution as it seeks to become a fully functioning, Living Digital Archive. And the journey of our teams (within the archive and our depositors) which have grown, matured and embraced a widening range of disciplines in response to the digital records challenge.

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I. INTRODUCTION (THE PROBLEM)

The UK National Archives (TNA) is the archive of UK central government, the courts and (from 2025) also the archive of the UK Parliament. TNA acts as a trusted custodian of the Nation's memory for the benefit of current and future generations. Under UK legislation [1], Digital Public Records of enduring historical value should be transferred to TNA's custody for permanent preservation (and access where appropriate) within 20 years of creation. The UK government formally embraced digital records management from 2004 [2], though some departments were

earlier adopters. TNA has consequently been archiving born-digital records for over 20 years.

Our early focus was on the emerging challenge of Digital Preservation. The mechanism for getting records into the archive in the first place was something of an afterthought. The only significant innovations in this process in the first two decades of operation were the introduction of checksums and switching our preferred transfer medium from DVD to hard drive as volumes increased. As a result of this neglect, digital records transfer to TNA was a manual, complex, inaccurate and inefficient process. In January 2019, the time taken from the selection of records for permanent preservation to their accession at TNA frequently exceeded a year. We saw long feedback loops and cycles of re-work as depositors struggled to meet our required standard of preparation and description.

This duration was excessive, and indicative of the challenges departments faced: in following the process; the level of support needed from our digital archivists; having access to the requisite technical skills; and managing the sensitivity, complexity and volume of records being transferred. In common with many digital organisations, our depositors were accumulating growing 'digital heaps' and it was increasingly apparent that the difficulty of transferring

records to TNA had become a significant barrier to archiving this material.

The digital transfer process involving hard drives is highly manual and demanding. After appraisal, selection, and sensitivity review, the transferring body informs TNA of their intent to transfer digital records. At this point they are required to undertake steps including completing an online digital transfer form, installing and using specialised software within their local working environment, creating metadata schemas and, finally, organising and saving their records on hard drives we supply. Upon receipt at TNA, the records are sanitised, verified, and returned to the department when issues are inevitably detected.

II. SERVICE TRANSFORMATION (THE APPROACH)

In 2019, we embarked on a journey of transformation into a fully functioning, living Digital Archive that is hungry for records [3]. In response to this vision, we stepped back and took a more rounded view of the services required to operate as a full digital archive (rather than primarily as a digital preservation function). The focus of our work shifted towards digital *Transfer* – the process of bringing digital records into the Archive – without which there would arguably be no digital archive to preserve or access. We set ourselves the goal of making it user-centred; easier to transfer than to delay; and for the entire process to possible to complete within a day, with an aspiration of just hours or even minutes.

This digital transformation followed some key principles which required us to re-think our established structure and practices and redefine the boundaries of what an archive does:

1) Service orientation: We adopted a service-oriented approach. Our digital archivists and infrastructure specialists came together to form a Digital Preservation service, and we created a new service for Digital Transfer (with the ambition of adding a third service in time for Access to digital records). This approach gives each service a focus, clear governance and maintains a separation of concerns. Previously our DP system was heavily customised to try to fill gaps in transfer and access – and as a consequence it did none of these things well. The new approach recognises transfer, access and preservation as distinct activities and frees each service to deliver its core remit.

2) User centred & multi-disciplinary: We brought together a full range of DDaT disciplines for the first time. The addition of User Research, Interaction Design and Content Design specialists ensured a firm grounding in user need and usability, to support our aim of making it as easy as possible to send digital records to the Archive. The pain points we identified included corporate barriers to locally installed tools (e.g. DROID [4] and virus scanners) and the difficulty of correctly structuring records on hard drives to match the supplied metadata.

3) Records focus: We aim to archive the best quality record possible. This means maintaining integrity throughout and taking the most complete and well described records possible, as early as we can. We are cautious that requiring high standards of preparation can divert attention from the fundamental need to bring records into the archive. Our approach is to do the best we can, we do not aim for perfection.

4) Incremental Agile Delivery: We follow the UK Government's Agile delivery guidance [5], progressing through stages of Discovery (or *Explore*) > Alpha > Private Beta > Public Beta (and eventually to Live). A clear definition of 'minimal viable product' (MVP) and incremental delivery ensures that each discrete improvement is consolidated, in use and delivering value early. This approach has helped us navigate fluctuating resources and changing priorities over the years, without wasted effort. We follow the principle of research, design, build, test, inspect, adapt, iterate and deliver.

For instance, when we initially designed the service, we did not anticipate receiving daily transfers of contemporary court judgment records. These differ from historical transfers in three respects:

Structural: Court judgments are transferred one document at a time, usually on the day the judgment is handed down in court. They are not 'saved up' or batched for transfer, unlike historical records.

Metadata: Court judgment documents are templated and self-describing, no additional metadata is supplied or required. References are pre-assigned.

User need: Users are court clerks and members of the judiciary rather than records officers. Our assumptions from user testing had to be revisited.

Nevertheless, we successfully adapted to these changes, creating a 'judgments path' within TDR to

enhance transparency, improve access to justice [6] and safeguard these critical records.

5) *Test the riskiest assumptions first*: The riskiest assumption when we embarked on improving digital transfer was the proposition that our users would be able to upload content, including sensitive content, to our public cloud infrastructure. Our research indicated that improving usability and speed meant reducing our reliance on hard drives and locally installed software. The ability to upload was therefore a key test of the viability of a new service. The organisation's appetite for this was unknown at the time – this would be our first 'cloud first' development and the first time that sensitive content would be held outside TNA's own infrastructure.

6) *New archival practice*: Traditionally, records managers conduct appraisal and selection on a regular cycle, with records batched up for transfer. The 20 year deadline for transfer of UK Public Records is typically regarded as a target date. We now encourage a 'little, often and early' approach to drive better preservation outcomes for digital records and improve process repeatability, moving from 'transfer as a project' towards daily, business-as-usual transfers.

We similarly revisited our own, internal, assumptions. Archival processing has traditionally been linear – it is a limitation of physical records that they can be in only one place at a time. In designing our new digital records process, we embraced the opportunity to work in non-linear way – whether at a technical level – carrying out concurrent virus checks and file characterization, or at a business process level – sending new records to our Catalogue, Access and Preservation services in parallel.

III. TRANSFER DIGITAL RECORDS (THE SOLUTION)

A. *The vision for a new service*

The need for a new service to support digital transfer emerged from the problems outlined above. An initial attempt to make digital transfer easier in 2017 had delivered no material improvement. That project took the logical approach of trying to address pain points but had not worked to understand user need or considered redesigning the process – akin to giving users a map to find the route and a ladder to surmount obstacles, instead of clearing the path.

Our vision for the new service grew from direct engagement with our transferring bodies to understand their needs and challenges. We proposed a

new digital service that would offer a streamlined and intuitive user journey and require no locally installed software or specialist technical skills.

The proposed 'minimum viable product' journey was as follows: A records officer logs in to the service via a web browser > they see just the actions that are relevant in their context > they upload records > the service automatically carries out all necessary sanitisation, validation and characterization > there is an option to add descriptive metadata if this is available > the transfer is completed at the push of a button > the newly accessioned records flow seamlessly to our public catalogue (Discovery) and our Digital Preservation service.

We have been working since 2019 to test and refine this journey with our users and to incrementally develop the service that was envisioned. The service is named 'Transfer Digital Records' (TDR). In line with UK government guidance [7], it 'does exactly what it says on the tin' [8].

B. *Technology approach*

Building, maintaining and enhancing TDR is a significant task and a long-term undertaking. The methodology and approach are as crucial as the actual development itself. There are important factors to consider, some of which are discussed below:

1) *Public cloud*: TDR was built as a 'cloud first' development, using modern public cloud infrastructure. Our supplier is Amazon Web Services (AWS) but we could have utilized any similar provider. Exit planning is an essential feature of any such development, and the team had to balance maintaining portability with the desire to benefit in full from the features offered by the infrastructure service.

2) *Serverless architecture*: TDR favours 'serverless' approaches, to enable resource optimization against a 'spiky' usage profile. This has proved beneficial in managing both service availability and cost. Again, there is a trade-off to be made, and we will need to revisit this as our usage profile changes. With hindsight we could have allowed targeted use of servers (EC2 instances) for high demand processing such as virus scanning, even in the current iteration.

3) *Design system*: The user interface incorporates components from the UK Government Design System [9], adding to this where needed. TDR has a different but complementary visual identity to TNA's

public facing website, to reflect its role as a service for government, not a public engagement service.

A key accessibility principle is *progressive enhancement* of the user interface. This is designed to meet the needs of all users, including those using assistive technologies. Enhanced features may be introduced for more modern browsers, but the core experience is accessible to all.

4) *Security*: This is a fundamental requirement. Our users require high confidence that transfers are secure and maintain data integrity. We undertake scenario-based threat modelling, commission external penetration tests and assessments, follow standards and embrace a secure-by-design approach to help provide assurance that we are building and maintaining a secure and robust infrastructure.

5) *Identity management*: User authentication for the application uses KeyCloak [10] with multi-factor-authentication. Our user research was essential to designing a secure approach without compromising ease of use. This solution is proving difficult to administer as take-up of TDR increases. It is not integrated with depositors' joiners-movers-leavers processes and is unlikely to scale well as TNA develops additional services for our government audience. We will review the use of Keycloak in 2025/26.

6) *Working in the open, supporting re-use*: All of our code is available for review and reuse, except where security concerns dictate otherwise. In practice it would not be trivial for another organisation to deploy their own instance of TDR – some technical skill would be required. We hope that by sharing our work we might save others time and effort in developing a similar service. We are open to external scrutiny of our code and welcome constructive feedback.

C. The TDR user and records journeys

1) *Log in and upload*: Once logged in, the user is prompted to upload. They select a single local directory as the root containing the records selected for transfer. This triggers client-side checksum generation (SHA256) and file metadata harvesting (filename, filepath, date last modified, via FileAPI). Harvested metadata is written to a database (AWS PostgreSQL) and the upload itself is triggered. Data is uploaded through the web browser; uploaded files are stored in an 'Upload' S3 bucket.

2) *Pre-accession checking*: An AWS step function is triggered which in turn triggers four *concurrent* Lambda processes:

File Format Identification: runs TNA's own DROID to identify & characterise uploaded files. The fail path for unidentified formats still needs to mature to flag these for archivists to research and add to Pronom.

Anti-virus scanning: runs a Yara-based malware detection engine. Anything that fails this step is moved to a quarantine area. Files that pass are moved to a 'clean' S3 bucket.

Checksum validation: Generates a new SHA256 checksum and compares it against the checksum harvested pre-upload to ensure there has been no data corruption during upload.

Related material: Identifies redacted versions of sensitive records and creates a relationship in the database between the (closed) original and (open) redacted versions.

3) *Metadata*: TDR creates a schedule of the uploaded records for the user to download and review. They can edit and resubmit this to add descriptive metadata and indicate sensitivities in the content.

In a change to our original vision of seamless, self-service transfer, the process is paused at this point for a digital archivist to review the metadata schedule. This is a risk management intervention to validate that expected sensitive content is correctly flagged and also that records are not marked closed without prior scrutiny. This manual step will reduce as we further automate this check.

4) *Transfer and pre-accession*: The user confirms transfer and triggers the 'export' process. Records (from the 'clean' bucket) and metadata (from the database) are packaged up in BagIt format and sent to an 'Export' S3 bucket. This in turn triggers a message (via an event bus) that downstream services can action. Actions include sending records to Access and Preservation via an ETL pipeline that will re-format and re-package them appropriately.

We have introduced a second pause before publication to allow digital archivists and (if necessary, depositors) to review the records on our staging site and confirm that they appear as they should. The records are officially transferred when the descriptions and any open content are published on our public-facing catalogue, Discovery.

D. TDR challenges, learning and further work

We wanted the process of digital records transfer to be as easy as possible. We prioritise usability and conduct user testing which in turn informs our design. The metadata upload feature was particularly hard to design, and multiple iterations were required to achieve a streamlined, highly usable process while maintaining data quality. There is more work to do in this area. Currently, metadata that fails our validation is rejected and must be re-prepared. Similarly, if non-record content is included (e.g. thumbs.db) the whole consignment is rejected for amendment and re-upload. We would like to enable users to amend records and metadata in-flight within TDR.

Archiving digital information is inherently challenging, particularly when assisting multiple depositors, each with their own records-management teams, policies and supporting technologies. Providing support for multiple formats – ranging from PDFs and Word documents to web-native objects – adds further complexity. For example, see the discussion of Google Documents in (IV-B) below. Managing executable code and other unconventional formats brings its own risks. Developing metadata schemas that accommodate diverse organisations while maintaining high usability for records officers who are more familiar with paper cataloguing, also requires careful consideration.

We are continuing to develop TDR to increase our per-batch volumes, improve processing speed and widen coverage to more types of digital records.

IV. CLOUD TO CLOUD TRANSFER

A. The case for cloud-to-cloud transfer

The TDR service discussed in (III) above greatly eases transfer of digital records held locally. However, depositors are increasingly making use of cloud-enabled productivity and records management services such as Google Drive or Office 365/SharePoint. Currently, transfer from these environments entails first exporting content to a local environment. This is error-prone and risks loss or degradation of record integrity. Dates are particularly vulnerable to being reset during this exercise and some key metadata elements (arrangement, user tagging) will not usually be captured by default. It also seems inefficient to download records from a managed cloud environment only to upload them to the cloud again via TDR.

B. First prototype: Google Drive script

Our initial focus for this work was Google Drive. This is approved for use by short-term bodies that transfer contemporary digital records to TNA. An example would be a public inquiry which is established in response to a notable event (often a disaster or other high-profile incident), conducts hearings, reports, closes down and transfers its records, all within the span of a few years.

A prototype Python script was developed to harvest records via the Google Drive API. This gives us repeatable, high integrity, comprehensive capture including detailed metadata and structural details (e.g. parent IDs, MD5 checksums for non-native content).

For Office or PDF documents managed within the Google environment, the script works well. Conversely, native Google docs present a unique archiving challenge. They do not exist as discrete documents but as data that is rendered in the browser. They can be exported, but a suitable format must be chosen, and this inevitably captures an imperfect representation of the original user experience. Our approach is to export the record in multiple formats, to try to capture as much of the richness of the original experience as possible. To date, we have archived Documents (as opposed to Sheets or other formats), exporting these as PDFs to capture the visual and structural qualities of the original and as Word to retain functionality and usability. Both representations together comprise the archival record.

This is not the same as creating derivative, format-shifted copies for preservation or accessibility purposes, nor is it a case of hedging our bets on the longevity of these formats – the separate and ongoing activity of understanding and actively managing preservation risk may, in turn, result in the creation of additional renditions over time.

C. Challenges, learning, and further work

Script-based transfers encounter compatibility issues due to updates within the Google Drive platform. The script has become a victim of its own success – developed as an experimental prototype, it is now in demand for exporting records for transfer. Its use requires some technical skill, but we cannot resource dedicated user or technical support. It has not been thoroughly tested at scale or with later iterations of the Google platform. Creating the script gave us valuable insight into the challenges of harvesting records from the cloud and highlighted the need for

supplier engagement and collaboration. For now, the script remains available [11] and we will have to invest this year to maintain it and address issues that have arisen in use.

V. SHAREPOINT TO TDR TRANSFER

A *Scope and approach*

While the Google script remains in occasional use, the learning from this work directed us down a different path. Our user research suggested that harvesting records from SharePoint would deliver greater impact for our user base and unlock more digital transfers. c10% of public records bodies use Google drive, but the vast majority, c90%, have migrated or are migrating their records into SharePoint Online [12].

The Google prototype work helped us understand the usability issues with a scripted solution and highlighted the need for good integration with the records management platform. It also prompted us to look carefully at the challenge of providing ongoing support for such a feature.

The SharePoint to TDR project seeks to establish a highly usable mechanism whereby SharePoint objects and metadata can be captured at their source and delivered to TNA through TDR with their provenance and integrity intact. We understood that the solution would be a multi-phased project which would make use of innovation already available in the market and leverage cloud technology for better scalability, security, and efficiency.

The project is proceeding in Agile phases: an initial 'Discovery' which explored the issue and challenges; an Alpha phase which prototyped and tested assumptions; private Beta phases to deliver functionality and integration with TDR.

B *Discovery phase*

2023: A Discovery was carried out in-house to scope the challenge, define the problem and identify the focus of future development. The challenges identified include: retaining intrinsic metadata; provenance; security; and connecting SharePoint (Azure) to TNA (AWS).

C *Alpha Phase*

Oct 2023 – Feb 2024. We engaged a third-party supplier [12] with expertise in digital information management and information governance. They

worked with us to explore the feasibility of our proposal and develop options. Based on technical, usability and resource considerations, we opted to pursue the option of a SharePoint transfer application. This would be a Microsoft-approved SharePoint plugin available on the Microsoft store

During this phase, the team defined core technical requirements and developed a prototype plugin. We investigated the following requirements:

1) *Authentication*: Implementing secure user authentication for both SharePoint and TDR to ensure that only authorised users could initiate and manage a transfer.

2) *Record selection and Transfer Initiation*: Designing and developing an intuitive interface for selecting records in SharePoint and initiating the transfer of these records to TDR from within SharePoint.

3) *Metadata handling*: Extracting the fullest possible metadata from SharePoint, without change or corruption. Allowing the users to configure the selection of metadata fields to be transferred, aiming to include user-defined tags.

4) *Upload*: Accurately uploading records and associated metadata to an AWS S3 bucket, maintaining data integrity throughout the process.

5) *TDR integration*: Minimising changes to TDR's user interface. Opening up existing API endpoints and creating new ones to allow transfers in from SharePoint sites.

6) *Completion and Verification*: Implementing mechanisms to verify the successful completion of transfers and providing feedback to users.

The Alpha delivered a proof-of-concept prototype which allowed us to refine the technical architecture design before full-scale implementation.

D *Private beta (i)*

July 2024 – Jan 2025. Work continued with our partner, with TNA supplying requirements and user interface designs and collaborating to solve technical challenges. This first half of the private beta phase involved an initial build of the connector, including setting up AWS infrastructure and configuring the SharePoint plug-in. Testing with real users gave us direct feedback that we will incorporate into the work.

E Private beta (ii)

Jan 2025 to April 2026. We will continue work in partnership with a third party to flesh out the connector with support for tagging and custom metadata and improve the UI. In this phase, we will fully integrate the connector with TDR in preparation for operational deployment. The design is that a user will select an option (such as "Transfer to TNA") from within SharePoint, choose their records, and proceed with the transfer. Authentication with TDR should be automatic, based on SharePoint user credentials.

The following are in scope for this phase:

Technical Integration: Integrate the SharePoint plug-in's end point (in Azure) with TDR. Our success criteria include performance and latency tests, integrity checks, and use of secure data transfer protocols.

Usability and fit with needs: Add handling for user-defined metadata tags, and de-selection of records. Ensure a seamless user experience. Ongoing testing with real users.

Commercial aspects: We are working to agree appropriate IPR and licensing for the plug-in to ensure we are free to develop it further and that that we benefit appropriately from any future commercialisation of this work. We will work with our partner to navigate obtaining formal Microsoft accreditation before deploying the plug-in into production

Monitor impact: Microsoft is aware of the project and has a good relationship with our partner. They will continue to monitor the project's progress.

F Challenges, learning and further work

Future plans for integrating the plug-in with TDR include integration with TDR's transfer dashboard. This will offer users the benefit of seeing and managing all their digital transfers in one place, irrespective of the channel used.

For now, records can only be transferred from one SharePoint library at a time. The connector leaves no indication within SharePoint of which records have been transferred – users need to manage this within their own business processes. We are also becoming more aware of limitations in numbers of files and file sizes.

Despite these challenges, encouraging progress has been made. We will continue to optimize the

transfer process, improve the user interface, and investigate features to streamline records management.

VI. OUTCOMES AND NEXT STEPS

Our work is already transforming the way we bring records into TNA. TDR is now facilitating daily transfers of public records, and more transferring bodies are being on-boarded. User satisfaction is high, and engagement is increasing. Volumes continue to present challenges for very large transfers (over 10k records) and are difficult to communicate – throughput is sensitive to number of records but also individual file sizes and overall batch volume. We aim to operate comfortably at batch sizes of around 10k records and this will meet the needs of the majority of our depositors. We will also be maturing our failure paths and improving the metadata upload function. We wish to move away from the Bagit packages for downstream processing and handle records file-by-file. We will also be preparing for the final assessment point for TDR to be released officially as 'live'.

For larger volumes and legacy transfers, the cloud-to-cloud route is likely to come into its own. Our original objective of extracting SharePoint records at source and delivering them to a designated end point without loss or degradation has been recently accomplished. We are confident that we have identified a usable, technically viable approach. Key areas of focus for ongoing work with the SharePoint platform include automated algorithmic metadata tagging to reduce the manual effort required by SharePoint users.

We expect to see the balance of records transfers changing from historical to more contemporary. These are more likely to include sensitive content, and we will investigate whether we can add value during the transfer process. For example, we could automate profiling of records in-flight to flag the potential presence of unmarked sensitive content. Or alert depositors to similar content that is already in the archive, but with a different sensitivity marking. Our aim would be to identify potential issues as early as possible, preferably before we take the records into our custody.

Beyond the mechanics of transfer, other barriers to bringing records into the archive remain. Depositors must select records for permanent preservation and review them for sensitive content. High digital record volumes makes this challenging but it is likely

that AI technologies will assist with this. We know that the requirement for ongoing access to archived records is a blocker to transfer, and we have, in parallel, developed an access service to ensure depositors retain access to transferred material that is not yet published.

VII. CONCLUSION

Today, born digital records are transferred to the Archive daily. These take various formats, arrive in greater volumes, are recent, impactful and attract widening public interest. Increasingly, these records are received via TDR. We still use hard drives for transfer, especially for large consignments. In parallel with the work described here, we have streamlined the hard drive process as much as we can. However, as TDR grows, we expect hard-drive transfers to become more the exception than the rule.

TDR has revolutionised the transfer service at TNA and is continually being improved. We operate in an ever-changing digital landscape and must proactively engage with emerging challenges, manage risks and adapt to user needs. This is continuous and never reaches completion, but provides opportunities for discovery and improvement. Our focus on progress not perfection enables us to challenge and even disrupt established practice. Digital processes are inherently non-linear, with digital records often presenting in a chaotic manner. Embracing this messy reality is essential. It reflects our continuous learning journey and commitment to growth and innovation.

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